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Abstract

The document presents the specification of the repository, which will serve as a centralized hub for health technology assessment (HTA) methodologies and evidence, supporting DHT developers, policymakers, and HTA bodies in making evidence-based decisions while ensuring compliance with evolving regulatory frameworks. The repository will incorporate core functionalities such as document submission, classification, compliance verification, controlled access, analytics and training resources. It will meet requirements for security, scalability, interoperability, usability, and sustainability. This document details the repository's design, technical specifications, and implementation roadmap to ensure it meets the evolving needs of stakeholders in the digital health ecosystem.

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the objectives of the ASSESS DHT project is to establish a sustainable, open-access European repository for Digital Health Technologies (DHTs), systematically collecting, classifying, and sharing evidence, assessment methodologies and stakeholder insights to enhance the evaluation and adoption of DHTs across Europe. The repository will serve as a centralized hub for health technology assessment (HTA) methodologies and evidence, supporting DHT developers, policymakers, and HTA bodies in making evidence-based decisions while ensuring compliance with evolving regulatory frameworks such as MDR, IVDR, and the AI Act.

The repository's design follows a multi-phase methodology, beginning with an identification phase that includes desktop research and a landscape analysis of existing repositories. This is followed by a conceptualization phase involving stakeholder workshops and surveys to define key functionalities. The iterative design phase will involve a rapid prototype, refined through stakeholder feedback, and finally, the validation and implementation phase will ensure alignment with real-world needs through external testing.

The repository will incorporate core functionalities such as document submission, classification, compliance verification, controlled access, analytics and training resources. It will meet requirements for security, scalability, interoperability, usability, and sustainability. AI-driven features, including NLP-based semantic indexing, automated compliance checks, and personalized recommendations, will enhance its capabilities.

The access and governance model consists of an open-access section containing publicly available evidence, guidelines, and best practices, a controlled-access section offering restricted HTA reports and confidential assessments for authorized users, and revenue-generating services that provide premium analytics, compliance tools, and proprietary data access. Sustainability measures include a governance framework to oversee repository updates and long-term viability, stakeholder engagement initiatives, and funding diversification strategies to ensure continued operation. AI-driven tools and continuous feedback loops will further enhance usability and decision-making capabilities.

Ultimately, the ASSESS DHT repository will be a cornerstone for harmonized, transparent, and efficient DHT assessment in Europe, fostering innovation and supporting regulatory compliance. This document details the repository's design, technical specifications, and implementation roadmap to ensure it meets the evolving needs of stakeholders in the digital health ecosystem.

1 Introduction

The ASSESS DHT project addresses challenges in evaluating innovative Digital Health Technologies (DHTs), including solutions incorporating Artificial Intelligence (AI) and those embedded within digitally transformed care pathways (e.g., telehealth). These innovations require context-specific assessment and reimbursement methodologies. The project aims to create a new assessment framework with specialised pathways for various DHT categories, defined through a novel evidence-based typology. This framework will enable uniform adoption of Health Technology Assessments (HTAs) across Europe, focusing on DHT development, data protection, data quality, interoperability, and cybersecurity. Co-creation with patients, healthcare professionals, DHT industry representatives, is a central approach, and the engagement of payers and ministries is further facilitated through a project expert board.

Task 6.5 focuses on achieving specific objective 8: implementing a sustainable, open-access European repository for Digital Health Technologies (DHTs), capturing and sharing assessment methods, evidence and feedback from Health Technology Assessments (HTAs). The repository has been conceived as an open-access European platform to collect and share evaluation methods, studies, results, and objective evidence of DHTs' impacts on health systems and outcomes. As such, it would systematically index shared evidence, processes, and tools to benefit DHT developers and decision-makers. By fostering collaboration through training resources and community insights, the repository will enhance the quality and acceptance of future DHT applications. The repository would also aim to capture adoption progress across European HTAs, including feedback on the ASSESS DHT framework's taxonomy and pathways for various DHT types and insights into how evidence portfolios are received and evaluated.

Over the past few months, we have been working in detailing this general framework and vision, aligning it with the project's work and eventually arriving at a set of functional and non-functional requirements that have informed the technical specification of the Repository. This document provides the specifications of the ASSESS DHT repository, guiding the development of its first prototype, ensuring alignment with shareholder needs.

2 Methodological Approach

The methodological approach for this task consists of several key phases. It started with an identification exercise of how needs identified by the project at the initial inception phase are being addressed today by existing repositories, if there are competing developments and/or if there can be synergies to maximise impact. which may in fact add value to our own development.

This was followed by a conceptualisation phase involving a f2f workshop with consortium partners followed by a short survey to capture needs and expectations as perceived by the team through the lens of the stakeholder segment they represent. This internal consortium set of inputs were analysed and discussed, in particular, with work package (WP) leaders of WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5 and has provided the basis for elaborating the Specifications.

The next steps will involve the development of a rapid prototype to be used as the main tool of an Iterative design, approach, which will include 2-3 consultation rounds with different user groups and plenary discussions to refine the design.

Validation of the specifications, the design and the actual populated repository will be performed with external audiences to ensure the repository meets community needs. Additional stakeholders, not represented in the consortium, will be involved.

2.1 Identification phase

At the onset of the project, our defined point of departure was the description of the Repository in the Grant Agreement, which is summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Baseline Repository Concept

Desktop research has revealed a variety of repositories of information that are tailored to supporting specific stakeholder needs directly or indirectly associated to HTA. While several representative examples were identified and are summarised in chapter 3, we did not find a repository rivalling the basic concepts and primary focus of the ASSESS DHT Repository, especially emphasising DHT assessment methodologies.

2.2 Conceptualisation Phase

The Inception phase is the foundational stage of the ASSESS DHT Repository, designed to capture and understand the needs and expectations of various stakeholders. This phase involves the following key activities:

A face-to-face workshop: This was organised as part of the consortium meeting in Seville in November 2024. Our point of departure has been the inception as documented in the Grant Agreement which was further informed by the progress made across the project.

Table 1 summarises the explicit and implicit strategic objectives that the repository should serve within the framework of the ASSESS DHT project, as they have been conceived in the Grant Agreement.

Table 1. ASSESS DHT Repository strategic objectives

ASSESS DHT Objectives	ASSESS DHT Repository Objectives
To deliver harmonized methodologies for assessing digital health technologies (DHTs) across Europe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ To be a resource of harmonized methodologies developed by ASSESS DHT and other similar initiatives. ▶ To provide tailored resources for HTA bodies, developers, health systems, and other stakeholders to ensure consistent application of these frameworks.
To Increase the adoption of trustworthy and effective DHTs by supporting innovation and regulatory alignment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ To make accessible detailed guidelines and tools for developers to meet regulatory requirements, such as GDPR, CE marking, and other relevant certifications. ▶ to make available tools for developers to self-assess their products over the development life cycle, against regulatory and certification criteria, during the lifecycle facilitating faster and more efficient compliance.
Provide evidence to support decision-making processes for the adoption of DHTs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Maintain a repository of validation case studies, impact evidence, and real-world performance data to support evidence-based decision-making. ▶ Provide health systems and policymakers with evidence and tools to make informed decisions about DHT adoption and reimbursement.
Engage with stakeholders to ensure the repository meets their needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Include forums, user contributions, and stakeholder insights to foster collaboration and continuous improvement of the repository. ▶ Provide instructional videos, training modules, and other educational resources to support stakeholder engagement and capacity building. ▶ Provide instructional videos, training modules, and other educational resources to support stakeholder engagement and capacity building.

The aim of this workshop was to elicit a collective vision and general requirements as they had developed considering the learnings within the project after almost one year of work. Questions to be answered included:

- ▶ What are the expectations of the Repository for your user group?
- ▶ What Information?
- ▶ Which services?
- ▶ What do you envision being the expectations of stakeholders not represented here today?
- ▶ What value would the Repository bring in a unique way?
- ▶ What would be the best use of the private space?

► How do you see this being sustained?

A first task was to deepen the discussion on WHO IS IT FOR? i.e., define the stakeholders to be served by the Repository and specifying the target audiences within the relevant multistakeholder community.

Figure 2. Stakeholder segments

A second step was to analyse the WHAT IS IT FOR? Figure 3 presents the conclusions of this discussion, setting out the general framework of its main functionalities and the type of content that would be needed.

HTA	Developers	Health Systems	Jurisdictions / local level	Other assessment bodies
<p>Criteria: What makes it a good DHT?</p> <p>HTA Assessment methodologies: How should this DHT be assessed?</p> <p>Third party assertions: What previous certifications are needed ?</p>	<p>DHT Requirements, specs</p> <p>Evidence requirements</p> <p>Self/third party Assessment, life cycle assessments</p> <p>Testing and certification requirements</p>	<p>Information for</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy support • shaping reimbursement policies <p>Evidence of value</p> <p>Evidence of continuing suitability</p>	<p>Information for</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decision support • Selection criteria <p>Evidence of value</p> <p>Evidence of continuing suitability</p>	<p>Criteria: What are the requirements in their scope?</p> <p>Trust framework, mandates etc</p> <p>Assessment methodologies, assessment reports, certification</p>
General information, training, videos ...				
Horizon scanning				

Figure 3. Potential Content for the ASSESS DHT Repository

This interaction with the consortium provided the basis for the preparation of a survey to capture and document perceptions and preferences and help prioritise functionalities of the Repository.

Stakeholder survey: A short, detailed survey annexed to this deliverable, was prepared to gather the input, requirements, and aspirations of the stakeholders represented in the consortium. In particular, this survey aimed to verify the value propositions of the different user groups, understand the key functionalities and features desired by the target audiences and gather insights on potential challenges and opportunity areas. Respondents were invited to primarily take the perspective of the stakeholder profile they most closely fit, especially when it came to the value propositions and the information and tools and services that would be desirable. This would allow for a more accurate interpretation of the results.

The results of the survey are presented in the following section and have formed the basis for the elaboration of the technical specification.

2.3 Iterative Design

This phase will focus on refining the repository's design through multiple rounds of feedback and consultation. It aims at balancing the varied and sometimes conflicting requirements of different stakeholder groups. This phase involves the following steps:

Based on the insights gathered during the Inception phase, an initial design draft of the repository has been created and comprises part of this document. This will be shared with different user groups for feedback within the consortium and beyond.

A workshop with external experts that have been registered in the ASSESS DHT data base will take place once the first version of the design has been confirmed with partners and will be dedicated to verifying the objectives, scope, functionalities and design of the repository. Invited experts include stakeholders such as HTA bodies, developers, health systems, local governments, health professionals, patients, academia, and other assessment bodies. Stakeholders will provide their input on the design, highlighting areas of improvement, additional features, and any concerns.

A rapid prototyping approach of the ASSESS DHT repository will be supported, focusing on iterative development, user feedback loops, and early validation to ensure it meets the needs of HTA bodies, DHT developers, and multi-stakeholder communities. Below are some structured ideas for rapid prototyping:

The initial prototype will focus on the essential features to validate the repository's utility without delay:

- ▶ Implementation of the ASSESS DHT taxonomy and lifecycle decision tree for DHTs for semantic Indexing & classification of content;
- ▶ Prototype Data Model
- ▶ Access control model to allow for stakeholder-restricted content or discussion fora if required
- ▶ Search & Filter System
- ▶ Submission & review, of documents
- ▶ Basic Analytics Dashboard to provide for insights on adoption trends, evidence gaps, and regulatory progression.
- ▶ Population with Sample Content
- ▶ Link to relevant DBs (see chapter 3).

The second round of design validation will be based on real-world use cases and challenges and will focus on content, services and usability with potential users from four tiers (HTA bodies, developers, payers as well as health professionals and patients). The design review will be conducted by both internal and external ASSESS DHT experts. Additional questions to be answered that will have implications on the final design include:

- ▶ Advanced integration i.e. APIs for interoperability with regulatory bodies and market access platforms
- ▶ Use of NLP (Natural Language Processing) to categorize and semantically index documents.
- ▶ Implement AI-powered recommendations for related assessments or missing evidence

A final round of validation is envisaged at the end of the project and as part of wider consultations within the project, as the repository will be substantially populated and will also become an additional means of making the project results available and integrated into the body of HTA related information. As project results will be maturing, in the last year of the project, questions relating to the positioning of the repository in the HTA information landscape for sustainability beyond the project roadmap will become very relevant. Questions at this stage are likely to include themes such as crowdsourced contributions from HTA bodies & DHT developers, automated evidence tracking using web scraping from regulatory databases and Interoperability with open evidence data bases.

3 Results

3.1 Desktop research

A brief account of the most relevant findings of the desk top research on HTA related repositories is presented below. These examples illustrate that there can be overlaps with the Repository, but also opportunities to interlink information made available through the ASSESS DHT Repository to indeed provide for a one stop access to targeted information for HTA bodies and manufacturers but also a useful resource for other associated audiences.

3.1.1 For HTA bodies

European Commission and joint MS Initiatives¹: The European Commission oversees the implementation of the HTA Regulation (EU) 2021/2282, which became applicable on 12 January 2025. This regulation establishes a framework for joint clinical assessments and scientific consultations among EU Member States, aiming to enhance evidence-based decision-making and reduce duplication in evaluating health technologies. The regulation mandates the creation of an EU-wide repository to store and share HTA reports and related information. This centralized database will serve as a reference point for Member States, health technology developers, and other stakeholders, ensuring access to consistent and up-to-date assessment data.

The INAHTA Database²: This is managed by the International Network of Agencies for Health Technology Assessment (INAHTA), and offers a comprehensive collection of HTA reports and publications from member agencies worldwide, including European organizations. It serves as a valuable resource for accessing a wide range of HTA documents, facilitating information sharing and collaboration among stakeholders.

The WHO Digital Health Atlas³ is a global repository of digital health solutions registered by countries and organizations. It offers insights into global adoption trends, evidence of impact, and case studies for digital health interventions.

3.1.2 For developers

The European Health Technology Assessment (HTA) Database⁴ is an initiative by Accessus Health, a network offering market access services across all European markets. It is a comprehensive resource, designed to support preparations for EU HTA assessments and facilitate market access activities across Europe. The database is curated by local experts and offers an up-to-date overview of relevant HTA and Pricing & Reimbursement (P&R) documents for each European country.

3.1.3 Examples of Repositories indirectly supporting HTA

PubMed and PubMed Central (PMC) databases for biomedical literature and open-access research articles, though not HTA specific, are essential resources for evidence synthesis, and methodological advancements and offer scientific studies and clinical trials that can provide evidence for DHT efficacy and safety.

ClinicalTrials.gov⁵, though not an HTA-specific database, contains information on ongoing and completed clinical trials related to digital health interventions, which can support post-market

¹ Health Technology Assessment https://health.ec.europa.eu/health-technology-assessment_en?utm_source=chatgpt.com

² International HTA Data base <https://database.inahta.org/>

³ WHO Digital Health Atlas <https://gdhub.unige.ch/implementome/projects>

⁴ European HTA Data base <https://www.accessus-health.eu/european-hta-database>

⁵ <https://clinicaltrials.gov/>

surveillance and validation and as such can be a valuable source of clinical evidence that HTA agencies and policymakers to assess new health technologies.

The **European Medicines Agency (EMA) Clinical Data Portal**⁶ provides clinical data used to support regulatory decisions for medicines and medical devices. This validated clinical evidence that can be used to support DHT assessments and regulatory compliance.

3.2 Survey Results

The survey annexed to this deliverable (Annex I) was launched in the period of 1 -31 January 2025. The whole consortium team was invited to respond; however, responses were to be collected at partner organisation level. In total, 14 online documents – one per partner – were created. By the end of the deadline, 12 answers were collected and processed.

The survey consisted of two parts. In the first part, partners were invited to review draft value propositions primarily from their own perspective and based on these to contribute to the formulation of the overall vision of the Repository. They were then invited to rank the importance and prioritise (i) information content to be housed in the repository and (ii) tools and services that should be implemented.

3.2.1 Value Propositions and the global vision

Annex 1 contains the detailed value propositions per stakeholder group as they have been edited after processing the results of the survey. Table 2 summarises these value propositions against identified pain points for each stakeholder segment.

Figure 4. Reciprocal expectation towards common benefit

It is interesting to note that the main players – HTA, including other assessment bodies and the manufacturers of DHTs – have reciprocal expectation from each other as illustrated in Figure 4, depicting quotes captured during the survey. There is therefore an implicit expectation that the Repository will serve an overarching objective of supporting the collaboration between these two actors to relieve main pains, while generating value for all stakeholders as shown in Table 2.

⁶ <https://clinicaldata.ema.europa.eu/web/cdp>

Table 2. ASSESS DHT Repository Value propositions

Pain Points	Value Propositions
Health Technology Assessment Bodies and other assessment bodies	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ HTA assessment criteria vary across EU countries, leading to inconsistencies and delays in DHT adoption. ▶ Uncertainty around evolving regulations (MDR, IVDR, AI Act, EHDS) and their interaction with HTA processes. ▶ Existing HTA frameworks struggle to evaluate AI-driven and telehealth solutions. ▶ Duplication of assessment efforts across Member States increases inefficiencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ A central hub for cutting-edge frameworks, methodologies, and digital tools to support robust DHT assessment, evidence generation, and harmonization across Europe ▶ Standardized criteria, methodologies, and shared assessment reports to align evaluations, enhance credibility, and foster collaboration across regulatory frameworks.
DHT Developers and Innovators	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ High premarket investment as the burden of compiling strong evidence (clinical, economic) before market entry is costly. Multiple submissions are needed as different HTA requirements across countries make it difficult to scale DHTs across Europe. ▶ Regulatory complexity makes keeping up with evolving compliance requirements (GDPR, cybersecurity, AI regulations) challenging. ▶ Ensuring high-quality, unbiased, and interoperable data for AI-based DHTs is a major hurdle. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Practical tools, checklists, and self-assessment resources to streamline certification, evidence generation, and regulatory alignment, optimizing fast-track adoption and market readiness.
Health Systems and Jurisdictions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Lengthy approval processes delay the integration of digital health technologies result in slow adoption of DHTs. ▶ Adoption of DHTs requires major organizational and cultural shifts and entails infrastructure costs, hence a high degree of certainty on the value of the technology is needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Validated HTA-backed evidence for DHT effectiveness, reimbursement decisions, and post-deployment performance monitoring, ensuring long-term value and impact ▶ Data-driven insights and cost-effectiveness assessment to guide DHT selection, policy decisions, and investments, aligning with regional health priorities.
Health Professionals	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Many DHTs lack clinical validation or user-friendly design, reducing acceptance. ▶ Insufficient education on using AI-based decision support tools and digital platforms. ▶ Digital tools that do not integrate seamlessly into workflows add complexity instead of reducing workload. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Resources for DHT integration into clinical practice, ensuring safe, effective, and reliable adoption in real-world care settings.
Patients and patient organisations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Unclear information about the safety, effectiveness, and privacy of DHTs. ▶ Not all patients have the necessary skills to use digital health tools effectively. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Access to trustworthy information on DHT safety, efficacy, and benefits, facilitating adoption of DHTs based on improved outcomes through patient-centered innovations

Pain Points	Value Propositions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Fear of data misuse and cybersecurity risks when using digital health platforms 	
Academia	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ The evolving regulatory landscape (HTA, MDR, IVDR, AI Act, EHDS) complicates research and funding applications. ▶ Difficulties in engaging with industry and healthcare providers to test DHTs in real-world settings. ▶ Translating academic findings into policy or clinical practice is time-consuming and often faces resistance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ A knowledge hub offering indexed assessments, methodologies, and case studies, supporting research, validation studies, and educational advancements in DHT assessment.

A synthesis of these value propositions can then provide for the overall vision of the repository:

ASSESS DHT Repository Vision

The ASSESS DHT Repository will be Europe's go to platform for digital health assessment, providing open access methods, evidence, and tools to support innovation and regulatory alignment. It will support harmonization of evaluation frameworks and certification consistency and will streamline adoption of digital health technologies including AI driven solutions. By fostering collaboration and evidence-based decision making, it will accelerate the safe and effective integration of DHT into healthcare for better health outcomes.

3.2.2 Information held and services offered by the repository

Tables 3 and 4 below show the prioritisation average score on a scale of 1 (low) -5 (high), per stakeholder representation group for information to be held and tools and services to be offered respectively. Where stakeholder specific resources are concerned, the perceptions of other stakeholder groups have been taken to indicate the value of these resources for target groups other than the intended primary users.

It should be stated that the intention is not to extract accurate scores, which would not be possible given the very small sample, but rather to illustrate that there is generally good agreement (with very few justified exceptions) across the consortium teams on what is important to include in the repository initial design and what could be considered as a nice to have. It is, for example, interesting to note that HTA bodies and developers prefer a more formal character of the repository, with low prioritisation of features such as user contributions, discussion forums and stakeholder insights. These features on the other hand are considered favourably by patients and academia.

This overall snapshot was presented, discussed and verified during the workshop following the processing of the results and was therefore taken as a general guide for prioritising functional and non-functional requirements, to be verified and validated with a sample of appropriate significance.

Eventually, any repository could be badly out of date in just a few months. It is therefore important to clarify that content not created within ASSESS DHT and not maintained centrally after the project end, should be understood as content maintained by several existing repositories at the source and made available in a single search through the repository services.

Table 3. Prioritisation of information categories per stakeholder segment

Information Categories	HTA	Pat	Dev	Aca
Core Frameworks and Methodologies (Assessment Framework, Taxonomy of DHTs, Evaluation criteria, Assessment Tools)	5	5	5	5
Stakeholder-Specific Resources	-	-	-	-
For HTA Bodies (Reports on DHT assessment methodologies, Guidance on applying criteria across jurisdictions)	5	5	3,3	4,8
For Developers: (Regulatory requirements, specifications, and evidence-generation guidelines, Testing and certification requirements)	5	5	5	5
For Health Systems (Policy support materials for reimbursement decisions, Examples of successful integration and adoption of DHTs)	4,5	5	3,3	4,5
For Patients (User-friendly summaries of DHT benefits and risks, Information on patient-centred- innovations)	4.5	5	3	3,7
Evidence Repository (Validation Case Studies Reports, Impact Evidence: harmonised third-party certifications, Real-world evidence of DHT performance after implementation, including ongoing suitability and value)	3,7	4	4	3,8
Research and Development Insights (Horizon Scanning and Gap Analysis Reports, Innovative Use Cases)	4	4	2,5	3,8
Collaborative Resources (User Contributions, Discussion Forums, Stakeholder Insights)	1,7	3	1	3,4
Policy and Regulatory Information (DHT Policy Frameworks, Legal Compliance Guides, aligning DHT assessments with European HTA core models, European and national policies related to DHTs).	4	5	3,5	3,8
Analytics (A well-organized database of indexed assessment results, Adoption Trends, Performance Metrics on the effectiveness, efficiency, and user satisfaction of evaluated DHTs.)	4,7	5	4	4
Repository Updates and Governance (Records of updates to frameworks, tools, and content, information governance documents, user instructions)	5	5	3	4,6
Press and media	-	-	3.3	5

With respect to potential services and tools that could be supported by the repository, services such as Data Analytics and Visualization, other AI powered services (translation, localisation, knowledge curation, linkage of criteria to experience of assessment, cross-MS comparisons etc.) and chatbox for personalised information provision, received less support and will be retained as nice to have until the next wider consultation round. Given that such LLM supported functionalities and tools are more and more commonly implemented in repositories (for example the EDITH knowledge base⁷, the Neuronet knowledge base⁸) and they play an important role in the repository sustainability, we will include simple demos in the first prototype to assess feasibility and potential usefulness with a wider circle of stakeholders.

⁷ <https://www.edith-csa.eu/edith-knowledge-base/>

⁸ <https://kb.imi-neuronet.org/>

Table 4. Prioritisation of tools and services to be supported per stakeholder segment.

Categories	HTA	Pat	Dev	Aca
Training and Educational Materials (Instructional Videos, Recorded sessions from expert-led events Training modules)	4	3	4,5	3,4
Decision Support Tools (Interactive Pathways, Decision Trees, Scenario Simulations, DHT Selection support tools, Policy Impact Simulations)	3,5	5	5	4,6
Advanced Search and Discovery (Semantic Search Engine, Personalized Recommendations)	3	5	2,5	3,2
Semi/Automated Compliance Checks	3	-	-	-
(Allow developers to upload DHT specifications or documentation, and assess readiness against key criteria (e.g., regulatory standards, certification requirements).	3	5	4	4
Data Analytics and Visualization (Impact Simulation Models, interactive dash boards)	1	3	2,7	2,4
Horizon Scanning (Integrate with live data feeds to monitor ongoing DHT adoption and performance, flagging deviations or successes)	4,5	5	-	-
Automatically detect emerging DHT innovations and methodologies, notifying users about potential future disruptions or opportunities).	4,5	-	3	3,2
Personalized Training and Knowledge Resources (AI-Powered Chatbot: Tailored Learning Paths)	2,5	3	4	3
Continuous Repository Improvement (Usage Analytics, Automated Content Updates to detect outdated methodologies or missing evidence and suggest updates).	4,5	3	4	4,6
Other AI powered services (translation, localisation, knowledge curation... please suggest)	1	-	3	2,6
Other (please add) Library of relevant scientific literature	-	-	-	5

3.2.3 Accessibility

There was very good agreement that the Repository should be compartmentalised to create three separate spaces with differentiated access:

Open Access (Freely Available Resources): This section would hold information available openly and would be made available free of charge. This section would include:

- General Information (Mission and Purpose, Overview of Framework and Taxonomy of DHTs, Guides for manufacturers, Pathways, Public Evidence Summaries)
- Basic Tools and Training (Assessment Templates, Introductory instructional videos, webinars, and general training guides, General overviews of emerging trends and technologies)
- Search and Navigation (Basic Search Capabilities, High-level summaries of repository content for stakeholders to explore).

Controlled Access Free of charge

(HTA bodies) This section would hold information which may include confidential information, will be securely hosted and access will be restricted to HTA bodies only. This section would be made available free of charge and would include:

- Shared assessments (Confidential Assessments e.g. preliminary DHT assessment, assessment reports, manufacturer evidence, shared experiences of use communication between HTAs)
- Verification of certificates service (verification of third-party providers certificates)
- Private Discussion Forums (Moderated, invitation-only spaces for high-level stakeholder collaborations)

(Health Authorities) This section would hold information restricted to health authorities and would be made available free of charge. This section would include:

- A compliance portal (holding detailed assessment reports relevant for supporting selection of DHTs)
- Reports demonstrating the health system benefits arising from the adoption of innovative DHTs, meeting set standards

Note: The vision is that this information will not be held by the repository itself but by the relevant HTA bodies and will be made available through interconnection with the relevant registries in a seamless fashion. It should be however stated that presently this is based on the basic assumption that (a) this information is collected locally by HTA bodies and (b) the ASSESS DHT Repository will be adopted by HTA bodies and health authorities as a trusted information hub serving the interest of the HTA bodies and health authorities. While the value of this section will be assessed and demonstrated during the project, its realisation in practice will require agreements across the parties concerned that are beyond the mandate and capacity of the project.

Controlled Access (Revenue-Generating Resources and Services). This section would hold information and offer information services at a fee. This section would generate value through advanced services that would access and process information from several trusted sources and issue reports of interest to a variety of stakeholders. The following are indicative revenue generating tools and services:

- Advanced Tools and Analytics (Interactive Decision Support Tools, Predictive Models, simulators to estimate the adoption impact of specific DHTs on health systems)
- Proprietary Data and Reports
- Role-specific dashboards offering curated content and data visualization.
- Automated Compliance Checkers for manufacturers

3.3 Three example use cases

We are examining below 3 example cases of repository use, build around the ASSESS DHT case studies. It is not intended that the Repository will implement the full described potential. Rather the use cases have been intentionally ambitious to reflect the potential that repository could scale up to in a sustainable phase.

3.3.1 Repository as a Regulatory & Evidence Hub

Scenario

A startup develops an AI-driven diagnostic tool that detects early signs of cardiovascular disease using EHR information and wearable sensor data. To gain a sustainable level of market entry, the startup must meet regulatory requirements, demonstrate clinical effectiveness, and navigate multiple HTA processes across European countries.

The startup is unsure how evolving AI Act and MDR regulations affect its approval process, which requires it to obtain expensive expertise. Different EU countries require separate submissions, creating delays and inconsistencies as well as cost. The company struggles to define the right clinical and economic evidence methodologies to submit for assessment in a way that this submission will fulfil requirements of HTA bodies across Europe.

The ASSESS DHT Repository

- Offers up-to-date compliance guidelines, helping the company understand MDR, IVDR, and AI Act requirements.
- Provides standardized methodologies for developers to use when evaluating AI-based DHTs, reducing the need to produce different sets of evidence when applying in different jurisdictions.
- Offers previously accepted (anonymised) case studies and real-world validation reports to refine its evidence submission that the startup can explore.
- The repository's compliance tools allow the company to self-assess its readiness against key HTA criteria before submitting applications.

Repository Components Used

- Semantic Evidence Repository:
 - o AI-powered semantic search allows the startup to query past AI-based assessments and extract best practices;
 - o Natural Language Processing (NLP) is used to categorize relevant regulatory documents, previous HTA evaluations, and industry reports.
- Automated Regulatory & Compliance Checker
 - o The startup uploads its technical documentation (e.g., clinical trial results, algorithm validation reports).
 - o The repository runs automated compliance checks against assessment criteria
 - o Provides a gap analysis report, highlighting missing documentation or areas requiring improvement before submission.
 - o Ensures that the AI tool's clinical, economic, and real-world evidence is mapped to country-specific HTA requirements (e.g. through interconnection with the European Health Technology Assessment (HTA) Database)
 - o Facilitates early-phase regulatory sandboxing, allowing iterative improvements before full deployment.

3.3.2 Repository as a Benchmarking & Decision-Support Tool

Scenario

A **pharmaceutical company** launches a digital therapeutic (DTx) app for diabetes management, offering personalized behavioural coaching and insulin dose recommendations. Payers are hesitant to reimburse digital therapeutics without strong long-term health outcome data. The DTx app must also comply with GDPR and cybersecurity regulations before deployment.

The company needs to provide convincing clinical and economic evidence to secure reimbursement from national health systems. The company needs to benchmark its DTx solution against existing treatments (e.g., medications, lifestyle interventions).

The ASSESS DHT Repository

- provides validated case studies and HTA reports on similar digital therapeutics, helping the company position its product effectively.
- Provides life cycle information support to ensure successful and compliant development
- Offers GDPR-aligned checklists and best practices to ensure compliance.

- Offers previous payer decisions on similar DTx solutions that can help the company refine its reimbursement strategy.

Repository Components Used

- Comparative Benchmarking System
 - o Uses the ASSESS DHT taxonomy complimented by additional meta data models, to classify the DTx solution by therapeutic area (e.g., diabetes, mental health) and Intervention type (behavioural coaching, medication adherence, AI-driven dosing recommendations, etc.)
 - o Provides a side-by-side comparison with previously assessed DTx applications, helping define its unique value proposition.
- Cybersecurity & Data Governance Compliance Module.
 - o Runs GDPR & cybersecurity compliance checks to ensure patient data encryption, access controls, and consent mechanisms meet EU regulations.

3.3.3 Repository as an Adoption & Policy Support Tool

Scenario

A **regional health authority** wants to scale a telehealth platform for remote monitoring of chronic disease patients; however, decision-makers need robust evidence to justify investment and ensure that healthcare providers can integrate the solution effectively. The health system needs strong economic and clinical impact data before committing to telehealth expansion. Ensuring that the platform integrates with Electronic Health Records (EHRs) and existing hospital workflows is a major concern. Clinicians are hesitant to adopt the platform due to lack of training and usability concerns.

The ASSESS DHT Repository

- Provides past case studies and validated reports on adoption of compliant telehealth systems, reducing uncertainty about their impact
- Provides tools such as interactive economic models to estimate long-term cost savings and efficiency improvements
- Provides access to implementation guides to align with technical and regulatory requirements
- Offers guides, webinars, and case studies to help clinicians integrate telehealth smoothly into their workflows

Repository Components Used

- Through links to the European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format (EEHRx) repository,
 - o Provides HL7 FHIR and SNOMED CT implementation guides for seamless integration into hospital EHR systems.
- Allows health IT teams to access real-world case studies of successful EHR integrations.
- Cost-Effectiveness Analysis Dashboard
 - o The health system inputs number of expected remote consultations, reduction in hospital readmissions and Impact on patient outcomes (e.g., lower mortality, improved chronic disease management)
 - o The repository generates an interactive visualization of cost savings, helping justify telehealth expansion.
- Healthcare Professional Training & Adoption Toolkit
 - o The repository hosts on-demand video training on telehealth workflows and AI-powered chatbot that answers clinicians' common concerns about using telehealth in practice.
 - o Tracks adoption trends across different specialties, identifying potential barriers to provider engagement.

- Policy & Reimbursement Documentation
 - o Automatically pulls the latest policy frameworks from national and EU regulatory bodies, ensuring health systems stay up to date on the horizon scanning
 - o Enables regional policymakers to compare telehealth reimbursement strategies across different jurisdictions.

4 User Requirements

Tables 5 and 6 below list an initial sheet of functional and non-functional user requirements to be implemented in the first prototype.

Table 5. List of Functional User Requirements

ID	Category	Requirement	M = must have N = nice to have
1.1	Document Submission, Storage, and Retrieval	The system should allow users to submit various types of evidence, including documents, datasets, and multimedia files.	M
1.2	Document Submission, Storage, and Retrieval	The system should deploy secure and scalable storage for all submitted evidence.	M
1.3	Document Submission, Storage, and Retrieval	The system should deploy advanced search functionalities, including semantic search and filtering options, to facilitate easy retrieval of stored evidence.	M
2.1	Content classification	The system should deploy integrate the ASSESS DHT taxonomy for Digital Health Technologies (DHTs) and other necessary taxonomies to support semantic indexing and classification of content.	M
3.1	Compliance Verification and life cycle support	The system should deploy provide templates and tools for self-assessment, compliance checks, and evidence generation	M
3.2	Compliance Verification and life cycle support	The system should deploy allow developers to upload DHT specifications or documentation and assess readiness against key criteria (e.g., regulatory standards, certification requirements).	M
3.3	Compliance Verification and life cycle support	The system should allow for third-party certifications to be uploaded and should track and verify certifications from third-party providers through their site	M
4.1	Open-Access vs. Restricted Content Management	The system should deploy a tiered access structure to balance open access with the need for secure and controlled access to sensitive information.	M
4.2	Open-Access vs. Restricted Content Management	The system should include a user registration module.	M
4.3	Open-Access vs. Restricted Content Management	The system should manage different levels of access for various user groups (e.g., HTA bodies, developers, health professionals, patients).	M
4.4	Open-Access vs. Restricted Content Management	The system should include user authentication and authorisation modules	M
5.1	Discussion Forums and Collaboration Tools	The system should deploy moderated discussion forums for stakeholder collaboration and knowledge sharing.	N
5.2	Discussion Forums and Collaboration Tools	The system should deploy tools for real-time collaboration, such as document sharing, commenting, and version control.	N

ID	Category	Requirement	M = must have N = nice to have
6.1	Analytics and Reporting	The system should offer a dashboard to provide insights on adoption trends, evidence gaps, and regulatory progression.	M
6.2	Analytics and Reporting	The system should generate reports on repository usage, evidence submissions, and compliance status.	M
7.1	Training and Educational Resources	The system should deploy an on line academy with videos, training modules, and other educational resources to support stakeholder engagement and capacity building.	M
7.2	Training and Educational Resources	The system should deploy AI-powered personalized learning paths and chatbots for tailored training experiences.	N
8.1	Interoperability and Integration	The system should deploy APIs for interoperability with regulatory bodies, market access platforms, and other relevant databases.	N
8.2	Interoperability and Integration	The system should ensure seamless integration with external systems for data exchange and synchronization.	N
9.1	User Feedback and Continuous Improvement	The system should allow for collecting user feedback to continuously improve repository functionalities.	M
10.1	Governance and Sustainability	The system should enforce governance policies for data submission, access, and use.	M
10.2	Governance and Sustainability	The system should support functionalities for revenue-generating strategy	M

Table 6. List of non-functional user requirements

ID	Category	Requirement	M = must have N = nice to have
1.1	Performance and Scalability	The system should provide quick response times for user queries and actions, ideally within 2 seconds for most operations.	M
1.2	Performance and Scalability	The repository should be able to handle increasing amounts of data and a growing number of users without performance degradation. This includes both horizontal and vertical scaling capabilities.	M
2.1	Security and Compliance	The repository should implement robust security measures to protect sensitive data, including encryption, secure access controls, and audit trails.	M
2.2	Security and Compliance	The repository should ensure compliance with relevant regulations such as GDPR, medical regulations, and other data protection laws. This includes proper handling of personal data and ensuring user consent for data collection and processing.	M
3.1	Interoperability	The repository should provide well-documented APIs to facilitate integration with external systems, including	N

ID	Category	Requirement	M = must have N = nice to have
		regulatory bodies, market access platforms, and other relevant databases.	
4.1	Usability and Accessibility	The repository should have an intuitive and user-friendly interface that is easy to navigate for all user groups, including HTA bodies, developers, health professionals, and patients.	M
4.2	Usability and Accessibility	The repository should ensure the repository is accessible to users with disabilities, complying with standards such as WCAG (Web Content Accessibility Guidelines).	M
5.1	Reliability and Availability	The repository should have high availability, with a target uptime of 99.5% to ensure continuous access for users.	M
5.2	Reliability and Availability	Implement regular backup procedures	M
6.1	Maintainability	The system should be designed with a modular architecture to facilitate easy maintenance, updates, and enhancements.	M
6.2	Maintainability	The system should provide comprehensive documentation for both users and developers, including user guides, API documentation, and maintenance manuals.	M
7.1	Information Quality and Integrity	The system should deploy validation mechanisms to ensure the accuracy and consistency of submitted reports.	M
7.2	Information Quality and Integrity	The system should ensure that information integrity is maintained throughout the lifecycle, including during submission, storage, and retrieval processes.	M
8.1	Performance Monitoring and Analytics	The system should deploy audit logs and performance monitoring tools to track system performance, identify bottlenecks, and ensure optimal operation.	M
8.2	Performance Monitoring and Analytics	The system should provide analytics tools to monitor repository usage, user behaviour, and system performance, enabling continuous improvement.	M
9.1	Localization and Internationalization	The system should support multiple languages to cater to a diverse user base across Europe.	N
9.2	Localization and Internationalization	The system should ensure that the repository can be easily adapted to different regional and cultural contexts, including date formats, currencies, and regulatory requirements.	N
10.1	Sustainability	The system should be energy-efficient by design, minimizing its environmental impact.	M
10.2	Sustainability	The development should implement sustainable practices in the development, deployment, and maintenance of the repository to ensure long-term viability.	M

5 Governance, Access, and Sustainability

5.1 Open-Access vs. Controlled-Access Resources

The ASSESS DHT Repository will implement a tiered access structure to balance the need for open access with the requirement for secure and controlled access to sensitive information.

Open-Access Resources: These resources will be freely available to all users and will include general information about the repository, public evidence summaries, basic tools and training materials, and high-level summaries of repository content. Open access will promote transparency and widespread dissemination of knowledge.

Controlled-Access Resources: These resources will be restricted to authorized users, such as HTA bodies, health authorities, and registered developers. Controlled access will include confidential assessments, detailed regulatory compliance reports, proprietary data, and advanced decision support tools. Access will be granted based on user roles and permissions to ensure data security and compliance with relevant regulations.

5.2 Governance Policies for Information Submission and Use

The governance policies for data submission and use will ensure the integrity, accuracy, and reliability of the repository's content.

Information Submission: All submissions will undergo a validation process to ensure they meet the repository's standards for quality and relevance. Submitters will be required to provide metadata and documentation to support their submissions. A mechanism, such as a review committee will be established to oversee the approval of new submissions.

Information Use: Users will be required to adhere to the repository's terms of use, which will outline the permissible uses of the information. Policies will include guidelines for citation, sharing, and the protection of sensitive information. Regular audits will be conducted to ensure compliance with these policies.

5.3 Revenue-Generating Services

To ensure the sustainability of the repository, several revenue-generating services will be offered:

Analytics Services: Advanced analytics tools will be available to users on a subscription basis. These tools will provide insights into adoption trends, evidence gaps, and regulatory progression, helping stakeholders make informed decisions.

Compliance Tools: Developers and other stakeholders will have access to compliance verification tools that assess readiness against regulatory standards and certification requirements. These tools will be offered as premium services, providing value-added features such as automated compliance checks and detailed compliance reports.

5.4 Content Update Strategy and Version Control

A robust content update strategy and version control system will be implemented to ensure the repository remains current and relevant:

Content Update: For centrally provided information, regular updates will be scheduled to incorporate new evidence, methodologies, and regulatory changes. A dedicated team will monitor developments in the field of digital health technologies and ensure the repository reflects the latest advancements.

For linked information the dedicated team will maintain a procedure for ensuring that linked content remains linked only as long as it remains trustworthy and updated.

Version Control: A version control system will be used to track changes to the repository's content. Each update will be documented, and previous versions will be archived to maintain a historical record. Users will be notified of significant updates and provided with release notes detailing the changes.

5.5 Ensuring Repository Long Term Sustainability

Ensuring the long-term sustainability of the repository will involve several key strategies:

Stakeholder Engagement: Continuous engagement with stakeholders, including HTA bodies, developers, health professionals, and patients, will ensure the repository meets their evolving needs. Regular feedback loops and consultation rounds will be conducted to gather input and refine the repository's offerings.

Funding and Revenue Streams: In addition to revenue-generating services, the repository will seek funding from grants, partnerships, and sponsorships. Diversifying funding sources will reduce reliance on any single stream and enhance financial stability.

Governance Structure: A governance structure will be established to oversee the repository's operations, including a steering committee and advisory board. This structure will ensure strategic alignment, accountability, and transparency in decision-making.

Continuous Improvement: The repository will adopt a continuous improvement approach, using performance metrics and user feedback to identify areas for enhancement. Regular reviews and updates will ensure the repository remains a valuable resource for all stakeholders.

ANNEX I: ASSESS DHT Repository: Survey on Stakeholder Requirements

Dear partner,

WP6 has elaborated a survey with sufficient detail to capture your input and aspirations for the ASSESS-DHT Repository. Kindly review all sections and in particular focus on your user group needs and your WP envisaged inputs into the Repository.

Your input at this stage will be used to draft the technical specifications that will be used to deliver the first fast prototype of the Repository. We will consolidate all of the survey inputs as a draft specification and pursue with you one round of further review by before we develop the fast prototype.

Please complete all the **blue fields** in the pages below and provide comments/suggestions to the **grey boxes** using tracked changes.

Provide an answer on behalf of your organisation. If you require multiple inputs by your team members, please coordinate with them.

Your name(s)

Your organisation

Date

Completed (mark with “Yes”)

Vision

If you would like to comment on the text above, feel free to do it directly in the box below with tracked changes turned on.

In ASSESS DHT we have committed to establish an open access European repository for collecting and sharing cutting-edge assessment methods, scientific publications, tools useful to a range of players in the DHT ecosystem and robust evidence of the impact of DHT on health systems and health outcomes.

The ASSESS DHT European repository for assessment methods and evidence of digital health interventions is envisaged as an online platform fully hosted, technically and organisationally by i-HD.

The repository aspires to deliver value across diverse stakeholder segments by providing tools, pathways, and resources tailored to their needs. It will serve as a hub for rigorous assessment reports, structured evidence sharing, and continuous inspiration for those facing the challenging task of further improving assessment methodologies to enhance health systems' value and market effectiveness. It strives to support evidence-based decision-making, foster innovation, and streamline adoption while remaining adaptable to emerging DHT technologies.

The ASSESS-DHT repository should serve as a one-stop resource for assessing, and continuously improving the evidence base underpinning the use of digital health technologies. It should therefore

hold a comprehensive and well-organized collection of information, tools and services to meet the needs of its diverse stakeholders.

Value propositions

Please comment directly on the document and/or insert additional inputs:

- do these value propositions echo your stakeholder perspective?
- Is there something important missing?
- Is there something that should be removed as being of less relevance?

Value Proposition for European HTA Bodies

The **ASSESS DHT European repository** will be a suite of digital tools and documents to help:

- Communicate a cutting-edge framework to support robust evidence generation and assessment for Digital Health Technologies (DHT);
- Provide clear, replicable, and practical methodologies for assessing diverse DHTs, including decision-making processes that enable paced adoption of DHT;
- Demonstrate how evidence from certifications or prior assessments can support HTA;
- Support further harmonization of data quality, interoperability, and assessment standards across Europe, through digitalized dissemination of innovative HTA tools and practices to support the work of those facing the challenging task of assessing DHT across the continent

Value Proposition for Developers, Innovators

The **ASSESS DHT European repository** will:

- Provide a set of tools (including checklists and more interactive digital platforms) to support compliance with evidence requirements for certification and recommended options to build robust evidence for HTA
- Offer tools for self-assessment to assist developers to optimise their evidence generation plans and to be able to understand the evidence base they should build at each stage of the lifecycle of their products, aiming to enhance ongoing suitability and alignment with health system needs.
- Support a deeper understanding of existing fast-track pathways through helping self-determine likely eligibility for staged assessment, and providing technical guidance on the types of evidence that ought to be developed at each stage of the lifecycle of a DHT
- Supply real-world-tested frameworks and case studies to guide evidence development.

Value Proposition for Health Systems

The **ASSESS DHT European repository** will:

- Provide evidence, validated by HTA bodies, of DHT effectiveness, supporting policy creation and reimbursement decisions.
- Offer tools for ongoing assessment of DHT performance after approval, once adopted and deployed, ensuring sustained value.
- Demonstrate value and outcomes to justify investments in innovative health technologies.

- Provide tailored information and decision-critical insights that align with specific and systemic needs.

Value Proposition for Jurisdictions/Local Governments

The **ASSESS DHT European repository** will:

- Help identify the most suitable DHTs for local adoption with detailed evidence and clear decision-making rules.
- Provide structured, actionable information to inform localized health system policies and investments.
- Deliver proof of cost-effectiveness and impact to align with jurisdictional health priorities

Value Proposition for Health Professionals

The **ASSESS DHT European repository** will:

- Supply resources for integrating DHTs into practice, including training materials and evidence of clinical outcomes.
- Provide insights into usability and suitability of DHTs for real-world healthcare settings.
- Offer confidence in the safety, reliability, and efficacy of DHTs through validated assessments

Value Proposition for Patients

The **ASSESS DHT European repository** will:

- Ensure patients have access to trustworthy information on the safety, efficacy, and benefits of DHTs.
- Provide clear insights into how DHTs can address their specific health needs.
- Facilitate the adoption of patient-centered DHTs proven to deliver measurable improvements in health outcomes

Value Proposition for Academia

The **ASSESS DHT European repository** will:

- Offer access to a semantically indexed repository of DHT assessments, methodologies, and case studies for research purposes.
- Enable participation in validation studies and framework improvements.
- Provide instructional materials to advance understanding and application of DHT assessment practices

Value Proposition for Other Assessment Bodies

The **ASSESS DHT European repository** will:

- Publish well-defined criteria and methodologies to ensure alignment of their assessments to HTA requirements

- Facilitate the use of common mandates and certification principles to enhance credibility and collaboration.
- Offer access to assessment reports and tools to strengthen their evaluation capabilities

Repository Information, Tools and Services

Please insert your answers in each column:

- Is this information category necessary and/or prioritised for inclusion ?
- If your answer is must have, or nice to have, is it realistic to include? What will be the source of information in this case , e.g. WP/task, external source etc?
- How important in your opinion is this information item on a scale 1 (low) to 5 (high)?

Information

INFORMATION CATEGORIES	Priority Must have Nice to have No need	Source Enter text / reference / link	Importance 1 (low) to 5 (high)
Core Frameworks and Methodologies (<i>Assessment Framework, Taxonomy of DHTs, Evaluation criteria, Assessment Tools</i>)			
Stakeholder-Specific Resources			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For HTA Bodies (<i>Reports on DHT assessment methodologies, Guidance on applying criteria across jurisdictions</i>) 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For Developers: (<i>Regulatory requirements, specifications, and evidence-generation guidelines, Testing and certification requirements</i>) 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For Health Systems (<i>Policy support materials for reimbursement decisions, Examples of successful integration and adoption of DHTs</i>) 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For Patients (<i>User-friendly summaries of DHT benefits and risks, Information on patient-centered innovations</i>) 			
Evidence Repository (<i>Validation Case Studies Reports, Impact Evidence: harmonised third-party certifications, Real-world evidence of DHT performance after implementation, including ongoing suitability and value</i>)			
Research and Development Insights (<i>Horizon Scanning and Gap Analysis Reports, Innovative Use Cases</i>)			
Collaborative Resources (<i>User Contributions, Discussion Forums, Stakeholder Insights</i>)			
Policy and Regulatory Information (<i>DHT Policy Frameworks, Legal Compliance Guides, aligning DHT</i>)			

<i>assessments with European HTA core models, European and national policies related to DHTs).</i>			
Analytics (A well-organized database of indexed assessment results, Adoption Trends, Performance Metrics on the effectiveness, efficiency, and user satisfaction of evaluated DHTs.)			
Repository Updates and Governance (Records of updates to frameworks, tools, and content, information governance documents, user instructions)			

Other (please add): _____

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Information Tools and Services

INFORMATION CATEGORIES

	Priority Must have Nice to have No need	Source Enter text / reference / link	Importance 1 (low) to 5 (high)
Training and Educational Materials (Instructional Videos, Recorded sessions from expert-led events Training modules)			
Decision Support Tools (Interactive Pathways, Decision Trees, Scenario Simulations, DHT Selection support tools, Policy Impact Simulations)			
Advanced Search and Discovery (Semantic Search Engine, Personalized Recommendations)			
Semi/Automated Compliance Checks (Allow developers to upload DHT specifications or documentation, and assess readiness against key criteria (e.g., regulatory standards, certification requirements).			
Data Analytics and Visualization (Impact Simulation Models, interactive dash boards)			
Horizon Scanning (Integrate with live data feeds to monitor ongoing DHT adoption and performance, flagging deviations or successes, Automatically detect emerging DHT innovations and methodologies, notifying users about potential future disruptions or opportunitie).			
Personalized Training and Knowledge Resources (AI-Powered Chatbot:Tailored Learning Paths)			
Continuous Repository Improvement (Usage Analytics, Automated Content Updates to detect outdated methodologies or missing evidence and suggest updates).			

Other AI powered services (<i>translation, localisation, knowledge curation... please suggest</i>)			
Other (<i>please add</i>)			

The Repository shall have an easy to navigate interface that helps the different stakeholders find what they need in ASSESS DHT – that is, a suite of tools produced by the ASSESS DHT project.

Accessibility

To balance accessibility with sustainability, the ASSESS-DHT repository can implement a 3-tiered structure: making essential resources freely available; providing secure information spaces for HTA bodies and Health Authorities; reserving advanced tools, data, and services for controlled paid for access.

Please comment directly on the document and/or insert additional inputs. Do you agree with the tiers and the different resources placed there. Provide your comments in the box below:

Your text here

The proposed tier structure:

Open Access (Freely Available Resources)

General Information (*Mission and Purpose, Overview of Framework and Taxonomy of DHTs, Guides for manufacturers, Pathways, Public Evidence Summaries*)

Basic Tools and Training (*Assessment Templates, Introductory instructional videos, webinars, and general training guides, General overviews of emerging trends and technologies*)

Search and Navigation (Basic Search Capabilities, High-level summaries of repository content for stakeholders to explore).

Other (*please specify*)

Controlled Access Free of charge (HTA bodies)

Shared assessments (*Confidential Assessments e.g. preliminary DHT assessment, assessment reports, manufacturer evidence, shared experiences of use communication between HTAs*)

Verification of certificates service (*verification of third party provides certificates*)

Private Discussion Forums (*Moderated, invite-only spaces for high-level stakeholder collaborations*)

Other (*please specify*)

Controlled Access free of charge (Health Authorities)

Compliance portal (*holding detailed assessment reports relevant for supporting selection of DHTs*)

Other (*please specify*)

Controlled Access (Revenue-Generating Resources and Services)

Advanced Tools and Analytics (*Interactive Decision Support Tools, Predictive Models, simulators to estimate the adoption impact of specific DHTs on health systems*)

Proprietary Data and Reports

Role-specific dashboards offering curated content and data visualization.

Automated Compliance Checkers for manufacturers

Other (*please specify*)